

ReNEW

D1.8- ReNEW Methodology
Specification for Resilience and
Sustainability v1

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Contributor(s)

Main Contributor(s)	Ramdane Tami - IRTX Mostepha Khouadjia - IRTX Fereshteh Asgari - IRTX
Contributor(s) (alphabetical order)	Marija Jović - ISL Wiebke Duhme -ISL
Reviewers (s)	Peter Geirnaert - OHB Kostas Zavitsas - VLTN

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Acronyms and Abbreviations	Meaning
CLH	City Logistics Hub
OHB	Opleidingscentrum voor Hout en Bouw vzw
MCC	Mobile Command Centre
DT	Digital Twin
GHG	Greenhous Gas
RSQF	Resilience and Sustainability Quantification Framework
IW	Inland Waterways
IWT	Inland Waterway Transport
LL	Living Lab
SF	SEAFAR
SIL	Safety Integrity Level
MCC	Mobile Command Centre
DIW	Douro Inland Waterway
CEMT	Conférence Européenne des Ministres des Transport (in French)
SF	SEAFAR
AIS	Automatic identification system
MCC	Mobile Command Centre
SCC	Shore Command Centre
CCNR	Central Commission for Navigation on the Rhin
IWT-DT	Inland Waterway Transport Digital Twin
CESAMES	Centre of Excellence on Systems Architecture, Management, Economy and Strategy
ICCS	Institute of Communication and Computer Systems

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1 Executive Summary

This deliverable is a continuation of the deliverables already produced in other sub-tasks and WP. For example, [1] established catalogue of hazards and vulnerability scenario and provided an overview of KPIs for sustainability and resilience. In [2], the authors propose a generic architecture for digital twin and integrated dataspace inspired by their experiences in DUET project and other digital twin projects, and [3] specified for each LL the high-level functionalities and classified the KPIs proposed in D1.1 to define suitable dataspace.

The Task 1.4 of the ReNEW project refers to the methodology specification for resilience and sustainability. It aims to develop a generic methodology to analyse, assess and prioritize the living labs initiatives for sustainability and resilience enhancements on both Infrastructures and transportation resources against the extreme events related to climate changes.

According to the GA, it regroups 3 subtasks:

- ST1.4.1 Common methodology for use case description, Resilience and Sustainability indicators definition: Aims to give a comprehensive view of each living lab use cases, their common barriers and specific challenges.
- ST1.4.2 Mapping Resilience and Sustainability indicators to assess current or anticipated interventions: Definition of the strategies, policies and mitigation actions and anticipated interventions under the scope of sustainability and resilience KPIs while ensuring the biodiversity conditions.
- ST1.4.3 Methodology for the evaluation of performance indicators. Provide an assessment framework integrated to decision-support making asset for the Digital solution of the resilient and sustainable IWT system.

In this deliverable we will look at each part going from use case description until the proposed framework for resilient and sustainable IWT system.

2 Overview of IWT system

This part provides a multidisciplinary high-level view of the operational framework of IWT. Figure 1 illustrates the IWT through a series of blocks such that each block represents important sectors or aspects which should appear in the IWT-DT. The main identified blocks are:

Climate and Hydraulic: these dimensions are fundamental for IWT, they are particularly depending on the weather and climate. The navigation depends on the morphology of the water. It is important to master hydraulic modelling well to achieve a DT that is faithful to reality.

Monitoring: it is the set of applications and techniques that feedback the information that makes it possible to monitor the state of the system. Information is of heterogeneous format and nature. It can be used alone or undergo processing and even merging to build more usable information.

Infrastructures: They represent the structures and facilities enabling the operation of IWT. They can be considered as the IWT's backbone of IWT, they play a key role in stabilizing the IWT activities.

Management decision support: it consists of an intelligence capable of processing, evaluating operating and predicting information, and performing multi-objective optimization to feed decision support.

The vessel: for the sake of simplicity, in this document a vessel refers to all types of ships used in river traffic. It can be characterized by its class, its specificities and its technology.

Figure 1: General overview of ReNEW IWT System framework..

IWT assets and features may be grouped under the following categories:

Table 1: IWT assets and features.

Assets	Type	Index
Infrastructure		
Fairway engineering infrastructures	Groynes, Training walls, Chevron, bridge, sills, longitudinal dike, over depth, rip-rap, scour hole, lock facility	
Fairway marking	waterway marking, signalization	Adaptation (Narrowing of Fairway, Shifting of fairway, Fairway realignment)
Port	Conventional, autonomous, cruise home port, dry port	
Wharf		
Quay Crane	Smart loading system, conventional loading system	
Load area		
Vessel		
Floating battery		
Unmanned Surface Vehicles (USV)		
Software's		
Mission Planning	Task assignment	
Climate forecasting	E.g., Copernicus, Euro-codex	
Hydrological/Hydraulic modelling	E.g. HEC-HMS	
Navigation		
Positioning system	AIS, Galileo	
Sensors		
Bathymetric survey of riverbed	Min fairway depth, width	
Navigability	Water discharge, water level, Bridge clearance, Min high under bridge, reference water level, high navigation level	

Assets	Type	Index
Maintenance		
Riverbed	Sediment, erosion	
Operational	Rehabilitation, Replacement, dredging, remove sediment	
Habitat		
species	Faunal and floral	
	Biochemical and ecotoxicological analysis	Pollution Carbon footprint Noise rate
Management decision support		
		Travel time (rability) Stop/blocking time Distance length Cost Absorption rate Continuity Capacity Stability ...

The elements of an IWT system have strong interdependence with one another, it is not possible to assess a disturbance of one element without considering its cascading effect. From perspective of the resilience and sustainability, the interdependence of the elements implies complex decision support and risk management [4].

3 Living Labs and Use Case Description

3.1 Living Lab #1: Ghent’s Multifunctional Synchromodality Resilient City Logistics Hub

3.1.1 Context

Ghent’s living lab is the first living lab of ReNew project, its aim is to create a flexible and resilient logistic system for multi-user and multifunctional purposes. The Living Lab will focus on the **impact of events caused by climate changes on the operations of the City Logistics Hub (CLH)**. It is owned by the Regional IWT Community and SEFAR Mobile Command Centre [OHB /SF].

The key challenge for LL1 as described in the deliverable D4.6 [5] is to set up a multi-purpose scenario which can automatically support IWT resilience during a crisis and its sustainability by allowing the synchromodality at the logistic hubs.

3.1.2 Location

This living lab is situated in the Belgium city of Ghent which is a medium-sized city with a medieval city centre with an intricate waterway system. In the lab area, the City Logistic Hubs we have a sea canal between Ghent and Terneuzen (Netherlands) with a large range of infrastructure.

Figure 2: The Covered Area by the Ghent’s LL.Living Lab Composition.

OHB has created two City Logistics Hubs in the city of Ghent to explore novel ways in which synchromodal logistics can be adopted to and from the city. These hubs are designed to enable freight to move over inland waterways using low emission and/or autonomous barges. To ensure this synchromodality, many transport modes are proposed including cargo bikes and electrical vehicles, that can move freight and people into and out of the city. Furthermore, when cargo arrives in the City Logistics Hub over inland waterways, upgraded infrastructures are allocated to load the cargo off the barge and onto the urban logistic transport modes.

These technologies will allow to improve the synchromodality of the transport, and on the other hand, provide support for increasing the overall infrastructure resilience in times of crisis. Such a crisis can cover different events: freight demand variability due to pandemics or dangerous events, low/high water levels, breakdowns, maintenance, etc. (see the deliverable D.1.4 for more detail).

In this living lab we will have the chance to test new infrastructure that allows automated sailing and automated mooring, and to build automated loading & unloading systems, managed by a Mobile Command Centre (MCC) as a backup with Shore CC in Antwerp and Rotterdam.

Figure 3: An example of a Shore Command Centre (SCC) at Antwerp (source: Seafar).

Special innovation will be investigated to build the urban boat as a “floating battery” which can be used as a mobile emergency power supply in times of a disaster. It will be able to connect with infrastructure, boats, vehicles, MCC, hospitals, when the grid fails.

The Ghent’s physical twin is composed of the following elements:

Floating platform and modular pontoons:

Considered as an emergency transport and urban battery with a certain capacity, the resilience-assist modular platform will be used as floating off grid power supply enabling stationary position even in high stream. This ship will be managed as an autonomous sailing ship with a remote control from the MCC and will be equipped with Hospital accommodation. This ship will be operated as a self-contained sailing ship with a remote control from MCC and will be equipped with hospital accommodation.

Figure 4: Example of a pontoon with a crane.

This platform is a floating pontoon with a modular land ramp, making it scalable to any size of the terminal intended and highly mobile to locations to link up as a ‘temporary smart bridge’ with rail or truck services. It shall be deployed with at least 3 existing vessels in autonomous sailing for platooning to carry away 70 people per vessel or 25T cargo per vessel out of the disaster area and bringing in rescue professionals and equipment.

Gantry crane:

Managed from the MCC for autonomous loading and unloading the vessels in cascade (FIFO system).

Vessels and ships:

The ships will be equipped with sensors to measure all necessary environmental data (temperature, level of water, air pollution, CO2 and Nitrogen Oxides (Nox)...). Their localization is given by using positioning and navigation system (Galileo/Egnos).

Figure 5: Basic model of the zero-emission urban boat with electrical propulsion for autonomous sailing with people and cargo.

Automated mooring system:

Allows autonomously mooring of ships at the port infrastructure under the loading/unloading system of cargo.

Cargos and containers

Characterized according to their capacity and size.

Trucks

Characterized by their type (Diesel, HvO, etc)

Trains

Characterized by their capacity, their origin/destination, occupancy, etc.

People (passengers, workers...)

Figure 6: Illustration of the automated mooring system.

3.1.3 Living Lab Stakeholders

The main stakeholders are the regional IWT community of Ghent and OHB/SF. The digital twin will allow to manage data from the sensors on OHB/SF data portals defining a significant innovation in data management by building data space as well as scenarios which can be evaluated.

Expert & Innovation Centre - OHB: will participate in the design of Resilience assist Modular Platform and pontoons (see task T2.1 from the GA) and will coordinate its implementation in support of LL1 Ghent's Multifunctional Synchromodality City Logistics Hub in close cooperation with Seafar and UGAL.

Seafar - SF: will support the integration of remote-control technologies to increase IWT resilience and the integration of such services into the digital twin solutions.

University of Galati - UGAL: is responsible for the design of resilience-assist modular platform and pontoons and will support associated construction and operationalization activities in the LL.

3.1.4 Living Lab High Level Need:

Main objectives

In the Living Lab at Ghent (LL1), the aim is to create a flexible and resilient logistic system for multi-user and multifunctional purposes. The Living Lab will focus on the impact of events caused **by climate change on the operations of the City Logistics Hub.**

We can summarize the objectives of the Ghent’s living lab as follow:

1. Implement synchronomodality solutions for cities based on infrastructure to improve resilience and sustainability. The City Logistics Hubs will synchronize the arrival of the freight over barges with various transport modes with a focus on quality of living and environmental sustainability. For this purpose, this living lab will offer technological assets to support this objective:
 - a. Provide a Mobile Command Centre (MCC) for managing the vessels with smart navigation, an automated mooring system, loading/unloading system of the ships and land material.
 - b. Design and develop a resilient mobile smart terminal allowing the deployment of an appropriate resilience-assist modular platform and pontoons. These resilient infrastructures could be considered as *emergency transport and urban battery*. By building-in a 10 T battery capacity, the platform will be used as “floating off grid power supply. This ship will be managed as an autonomous sailing ship with remote control from the MCC.
2. Improve energy resilience with power solutions innovations with the help of floating batteries.
3. Experiments, test and demonstrate the digital twin solutions in a real-life environment with the application scenarios which will allow the evaluation of the short and long terms impacts of climate disaster on the City Logistics Hub.

3.1.5 Living Lab High Level Requirements

The table below regroups some requirements that we have identified for the Ghent living labs use case and scenarios:

Table 2: High Requirements for the Ghent living lab use cases.

High Level Requirement	Physical domain	Functional domain	Short Description
Requirement #1	Floating battery	Energy Management	When battery is almost empty it can sail away to get connected to the off-grid power supply as Solar panel park, windmills, etc.
Requirement #2	Sensor measurement anomaly	Warning Management	Alarm system must be notified to the government alert institutions
Requirement #3	Assistance	Emergency plan	Existing emergency plans by the Belgian and Flemish governments, that can be reviewed and

			adapted to the tests in the LL.
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3.1.6 Use cases

The main interest of the Ghent living lab is to measure the **impact of the climate disasters on the City Logistic Hub** and set up mitigation actions and alternatives to minimize this impact on the IWT system. This can be leveraged by testing new infrastructure that enables automated sailing and automated mooring, and to develop automated loading & unloading systems. In addition to investigating the construction of urban boat as a “floating battery” which can be used as a mobile emergency power supply. This use case covers different scenarios related to the climate disasters that could impact the infrastructure and traffic and where the objective is to map the resilience of the existing and deployed infrastructures as a response to the emergency plans setup. Among these scenarios, we find:

- **Impact of floods in a dense area or city environment:** Rescue of people and material in a rapid deployment of the ships on an automated level managed by the MCC.
- **Impact of floods on the logistic infrastructure:** Move the MCC out of the disaster area within 1 hour towards the fixed Command Centre. Setting up an alternative infrastructure out of the danger zone.
- **Impact of the loss of staff in the Smart Terminal:** Allow the deployment of automation of the vessels, mooring system and infrastructure (cranes, loading/unloading system) in 3 hours.
- **Impact of road obstruction:** Operate small vessel in platooning for the rescue and evacuation of people.
- **Impact of water-obstruction:** Remove obstacles in the water while blocking the waterway by using automated vessels (with crane on board if possible) to clear the waterway.
- **Impact of failure of the electricity grid system:** Quantify the readiness level to unfold the “floating battery vessel” in 3 hours as emergency power supply.
- **Use of the “floating power supply” vessel:** Operate vessel as a power supply for other vessels and when the battery is almost empty it can sail away to get connected to the off-grid power supply as Solar panel park, windmills, etc.

More details on the LL1 implementation plan, its organization and expected outcomes can be found in the deliverable D4.6- LL1 Ghent's Multifunctional Synchromodality City Logistics Hub v1 of the ReNEW project.

3.2 Living Lab #2 – Smart Douro Inland Waterway management

3.2.1 Context:

The second living lab of the ReNEW is the Douro living lab. According to ReNEW's objective for resilient and sustainable IWT, the objective of this living lab is to create means to take actions both for illegal wastewater dumping and investigate/simulate the river behaviour in extreme weather conditions.

Figure 7: Douro River from ReNEW webpage.

A detailed overview of the living lab use cases and requirements can be found in the deliverable D4.9-LL2 Douro River Waterway v1.

3.2.2 Location:

The location of this living lab is on the Douro River, in northern Portugal, covering the entirety of the Portuguese waterway (208 km from the border until the mouth of the river in Porto). It is included in the TEN-T feeding point of the Atlantic Corridor connecting with the inner side of the North and Centre regions in Portugal.

3.2.3 Living Lab's High-Level Requirements:

- The digital twin models the river behaviour, by using the extensive real-time data flow produced by different sensors. The model will be used especially for drought and flood analysis and real time prediction.

- In specific situations: The river behaviour model developed in ReNEW, will help APDL to improve the existing meteorological and hydrological models in responding to what-if simulations.
- In Normal situation: the extensive real-time data flow produced by different sensors ensure the pre-approved navigation plan followed by the vessels to prevent cascading effects such as river pollution.
- Smart contract, (Between APDL and each vessel owner) is a solution to mimic the navigation plan of each ship to promote the respect of navigation rules and thus a healthy ecological behaviour.

3.2.4 Living lab Use cases:

Two main use cases have been identified for the Douro Living lab, these two use cases are:

- **Illegal wastewater dumping**

The objective of this case is to prevent illegal wastewater dumping. This is attainable by using extensive real-time data coming from several sensors which ensure the predefined navigation plan and locking timetable. In addition, using smart contracts encourages the Compliance with Douro inland navigation rules and environmental protection.

- **River behaviour simulation for extreme weather condition**

The objective in this use case is to use the vast amount of real-time data collected from different sensors to simulate the river behaviour for near real-time predictions. This will help the stakeholders to improve the responsiveness to different what-if scenarios.

3.2.5 Living lab Stakeholders:

Directorate-General for Natural Resources, Safety and Maritime Services (DGRM) is considered as a key stakeholder in taking measures and actions in case of any emergency situation. Furthermore, they are responsible for the ships and relevant equipment certifications regarding tampering risks to sensors and GPS. APDL as the river navigation authority is another key stakeholder who conducts the smart contracts for each vessel owner to monitor the wastewater dumping and fine in case of illegal acts.

3.3 Living Lab #3 - Planning mitigation demonstrator app for climate resilient and environmentally sustainable transport infrastructure

3.3.1 Context

In the context of climate change, the challenge of efficient transport management and carbon footprint reduction is more urgent than ever. The optimization and improvement of IWT is a leverage that EU supports due to its latent potential. To reach such purpose, this LL intends to build a planning proactive framework and develop an agile synchro-modal solution that connects several cities in different countries through arteries in the inland waterway system. On the one hand, the undertaken development aims to increase shipping efficiency and logistic performance. On the other hand, it is expected to strengthen the reliability and resilience of the infrastructure during a disruptive event. Therefore, it is important to create synergy between planning tools and the information on the current and future state of the network.

More details about the living lab 3 can be found in the deliverable D.4.12- LL3 Planning mitigation for climate resilient and sustainable transport infrastructure boosting modal shift v.

3.3.2 Location

The target operating area is located in East and North corridors on the Netherlands. The network may be extended to France, Belgium, and Austria. The cities considered in the network are: Antwerp - Paris - Liege - Venlo - Nijmegen – Rotterdam [LL #3].

Figure 8: LL3 area [ReNEW Grant Agreement].

3.3.3 LL users

This LL3 involves different stakeholders which are the actors of inland waterway logistic as depicted in Figure 9. The forwarder is the organization that links between client and shipper. The shipper is the entity that hands and transports goods. The skipper is the captain of the vessel transporting the goods. The terminal operator is the entity which manages the transit and the movement of the vessels through the terminal.

Figure 9: LL3's environmental diagram.

Blue Wave platform (provided by PANTEIA) is an application with several capabilities that will work in synergy with the IWT-DT, it enables to:

- host and establish digital contracts and transport documents between shipper and forwarder;
- provide traffic information;
- notifies skippers;
- display tracking and tracing of ships and cargo;
- and monitors the states of ships and cargo.

3.3.4 Living labs high level needs

This Living Lab expects to solve several technical issues such as:

- Use of real-time data in the planning task;
- Enabling regulated and secure collaboration and data exchange between stakeholders;
- Acquire operating data from infrastructures, vessels whether to monitor the system and service state;
- Develop a planning mitigation module based on multi-criteria objectives such as time, cost, and CO2 emission;

- Extended the planning solution by modal shift capabilities.

According to GA, the resilience approach and the mitigation solutions developed for this LL will be tested on a large scale involving 10 shippers, 10 terminal operators, and 100 shipowners.

3.4 Living Lab #4 –Resilience promoting Autonomous zero-emissions barges

3.4.1 Context

The 4th living lab of the ReNEW project proposes to use an autonomous X-barge to demonstrate and test the improved resilience of IWT infrastructure. The main objective of the living lab is to prove the economic feasibility and competitiveness together with the climate resilient characteristics of CEMT class 4 autonomous zero-emission vessels.

A detailed overview on the living lab 4 use cases, needs and requirements can be found in the deliverable D4.15- LL4 Autonomous Zero Emission Barge v1.

3.4.2 Location:

The location of this living lab is the actual waterways from Ghent (Belgium) to Duisburg (Germany), passing from the Netherlands. (Passing through the waterways managed by 3 countries)

Figure 10: Photo of X-barge from Zulu's webpage.

Challenge: The X-barges are designed (an example of a designed X-barge is presented Figure 10) to operate when the water level is low. They are designed to be autonomous, with no crew on board and to achieve these objectives many tests should be performed in 3 phases. 1) crewed 2) AI directed-with crew on board for intervention 3) no crew on board.

The IWT 4.0 Barge (X-barge), has 4 development aspects to improve the resilience of IWT:

- **Size**, The X-barge is CEMT class4 sized barge. The idea of restricted barge size is to allow the operation in shallow waters to insure the resilience to climate change.
- **Alternative propulsion**, The X-barge will be electrically propelled with modular powerpacks delivering the necessary power (hybrid propulsion)
- **Autonomy**, for example, a situation of no crew on board during transit, allows for keeping operations during the crisis, saving in operation costs and improving economic efficiency.
- **Digital connectivity**, as a key element for the living lab, the Digital connectivity between barges, infrastructure and terminal/ports allows for effective sailing plans, better traffic and logistics management, and thus fewer problems due to communication issues.

3.4.3 Digital Twin Requirements:

- Measure the efficiency (hydraulic & hydrodynamic) of the vessels used in LLs.
- Measure the overall impact of a full transport system, consisting of:
 - (a) Road transports
 - (b) Waterway transport with class V barges or larger
 - (c) Waterway transport with class IV barges (X-barges type)
 - (d) Waterway transport with smaller vessels (e.g., class II)
- Required adaption with: (Some are in common with LL1)
 - mooring system
 - Lock passing procedure and systems
 - Alternative energy bunkering
 - Digital communication with logistic management (VTS), infrastructure and terminals/ports

The important KPIs for this living lab are:

- Reduction in total erosion compared to conventional class V or higher crafts.
- Reduction in CO2 emission compared to a) Road network and b) Conventional barges of class V or higher.
- The overall cargo throughput (timeline and volume) impacted by flood to reduced water levels.
- The overall cargo throughput (timeline and volume) impacted by sudden obstacles (such as closed bridge) in a main waterway in cases of b to d
- General performances of cargo transport (frequency, timeline, Volume) for all the 4 cases

3.4.4 Living lab Stakeholders:

As the X-barges to be used in this living lab are under construction, the Zulu Associates is one of the main stakeholders of the project. Additionally, the collaboration with LL1 is previewed to use the expertise of SINTEF Ocean on autonomous vessels and autonomous mooring system.

3.4.5 Use cases:

For the use cases of this living lab the X-barge shall be used. The under-production X-barge is expected to be completed in the second half of the 2024. Once the X-barge is operational, different tests will be conducted to assess the resilience of the new X-barges compared to other classes of the vessels.

- **Use of the vessels from Ghent to Duisburg.** It is not feasible to do a full-scale test; thus, the concept verification will be a combination of physical and simulation. And the resilience of the magnetic mooring system, modelling the ways and the effect of barge on the ship will be investigated.

4 A Common Framework for Resilience and Sustainability of IWT

In order to define the ReNEW framework for sustainability and resilience for the IWT, we will be relying on a system architecture and modelling framework approach based on CESAMES (Center of Excellence on Systems Architecture, Management, Economy and Strategy) systems architecting methods (CESAMES) [6]. It is currently one of the *most used and disseminated* model-based systems architecting framework which is fundamentally oriented to support the development of complex integrated systems. It is operationally deployed in various industries covering aeronautics, automotive, civil engineering, defence, energy, health, railway and space.

The CESAMES systems architecting framework is intended to be organized in the three pyramidal layers, as illustrated in Figure 11.

Figure 11: Illustration of the three architectural views.

The three systems architectural visions behind will be our key systems architecting tool for passing from living labs needs to the solution product of the R&S-IWTS (Resilient and Sustainable Inland Waterways Transport Systems). For that purpose, each of the architectural vision try to answer to one question:

- Operational vision: Why does the system exist?

- Functional vision: What is doing the system? and
- Organic vision: How is formed the system?
- Below we first present the surrounding environment of our product system, then for each living lab we provide a decomposition of our system according to the chosen architecting approach.

4.1 System environment

Before designing the different architectural views, we need first to introduce the environment for the targeted resilient and sustainable IWT system “S” or more precisely its systemic environment. This reference environment corresponds to the smallest and most useful systemic environment that results from the integration of S and all other real systems that have an influence on its design and development. It allows us to define its border, or in other terms what is inside and what is outside the system.

If we consider the different living labs, we can illustrate the key concept of its IWT system environment as depicted below in Figure 12:

Figure 12: Environment of the Resilient & Sustainability IWT System.

4.2 Architectural view

The heterogeneity of the environment of the system requires addressing it by different axes of architectural analysis in order to integrate the whole set of various perceptions provided by the different stakeholders.

As a matter of fact, each integrated system S can always be completely analysed from three different and complementary perspectives that generate three generic architectural views which give a better understanding of the design and the development of the system.

4.2.1 Operational view

Its core motivation is to understand in that way the motivation – that is to say the “Why” – of the system. It provides “black box” models of a given system where one does not describe the system of interest, but rather its mission, its interactions and interfaces with its environment.

4.2.2 Functional view

Its core motivation is to elicit in that way the behaviour – that is to say the “What” – of the system. It provides “grey box” models of a given system of interest where one begins to apprehend the inside of the considered system, but only in terms of input/output abstract behaviours and not of concrete implementation choices, in order to begin understanding more deeply what the system does, without however knowing at this point how it is concretely implemented through components. When we talk about digital twin, this functional view can be broken down into different layers by following a standard such as ISO 23247¹ as follow:

- (i) The lowest layer describes the observable Inland waterways elements. This layer describes the items on the IWT that need to be modelled. Officially it is not part of the framework because it already exists.
- (ii) The second layer is the device communication entity. This layer collates all the state changes of the observable elements and sends control programs to those elements when adjustments become necessary.
- (iii) The third layer is the digital twin entity. This layer models the digital twins. It reads the data collated by the device communication entity and uses the information to update its models.
- (iv) The fourth layer contains user entities. These are applications that use the digital twins to make your inland waterways more resilient and sustainable. It could be applications for monitoring or supervising the IWT system or applications that make processes work more quickly.
- (v) Cross system entity. This entity is dedicated to synchronize data and to ensure the security of transfer.

4.2.3 Organic view

Its core motivation is to elicit in that way the concrete structure – that is to say the “How” – of the considered system. It provides white box models of a system where one describes all concrete hardware, software, and components of a given system with their interactions. In the ISO 23247

¹ <https://www.ap238.org/iso23247/>

standard this view corresponds to the low-level layer that regroups all the observed entities that belong to the IWT system.

In the sections below, we describe these different views for each of the Living lab R&S-IWT systems.

4.3 Living Lab #1 Architectural Views

4.3.1 Operational view

Figure 13: Operational view of LL1

4.3.2 Functional & organic views

Figure 14: Functional & Organic views of LL1.

Based on the operational view presented in Figure 13, we can break down the functional view of our system into four layers. Each layer corresponds to an abstraction level passing from the user entity to the observed entity which composes the system at an elementary level. We can summarize this architectural view as flow:

User entity:

At the user entity we find the **User Interface (UI)** that allows the introduction of the desired threat and vulnerability scenarios from the scenarios library that regroups climate change, flood and terminal threats and risks.

Core entity:

This layer provides all the processes and analysis functionalities covering management and decision as well as the simulation models. For the **management and decision**, we find the support-decision making functions which include: (i) rerouting and re-planning vessel trips, (ii) deployment of emergency plans (iii) mitigation actions, or (iv) maintenance strategies. For the **simulation** part, we find hydrological, hydraulic and more generally climate change models.

Data collection and device control entity:

It regroups the **data collection** and **remote-control mechanisms** from the elements that compose the IWT system. All the gathered data will be integrated to the **data space** of the digital twin solution and will serve the previous layers as an input for their functionalities. The MCC plays an important role in feeding the data space. It is in charge of managing and connecting all the data from the infrastructure, boats, vehicles, hospitals, when the grid fails. OHB/SF are expected to provide data streams via their data portals and APIs that will include:

- Smart navigation data with all vessels
- Copernicus and GALILEO/EGNOS for positioning and navigation
- Smart automation of the onshore equipment:
 - Autonomous mooring system to let the ships autonomously moor under the loading system
 - Autonomous loading system that allows charge or discharge of the vessels during the loading time.
- Gantry crane for autonomous loading and unloading of the vessels in cascade.

4.3.3 Organic view

Elementary and **physical twin components** or what we call observable elements of the IWT system involving vessels, automated control systems (crane, mooring...) infrastructure, energy support and emergency accommodations such as smart floating platform and pontons.

4.4 Living Lab #2 Architectural Views

4.4.1 Operational view

Figure 15: Operational view for LL2.

4.4.2 Functional & organic views

Figure 16 presents the functional and organic view for LL2. The three layers of the functional view can be presented as follows:

User entity:

The user interface allows users to select several scenarios based on their requirements and also access to different data via DIW portal.

Core entity:

The core entity contains processes and analysis for all the aspects of the LL which are categorized into four different classes: Smart contract, Operational checking, resilience analysis, and different models used in the LL.

Data connection and device control

This layer on the one hand acquires sensor data and feeds both the core entity layer and the user layer and on the other hand, can transfer commands from the core entity or user interface to the devices in the real world.

Figure 16: Functional & organic views of LL2.

4.5 Living Lab #3 Architectural Views

4.5.1 Operational view

Figure 17: Operational view for LL3.

4.5.2 Functional view

As depicted in Figure 18, ISO 23247 proposes an architecture to facilitate the development and deployment of digital twin. The proposed architecture is organized into 3 layers:

User entity

Represents a set of functionalities dedicated to the stakeholders and users. The interface layer contains the tools that enable the user to interact with the DT. It is also expected from this layer to allow the integration with third-party applications that interface with the DT, such as Blue Wave app, and serve as the gateway with the external Data lake.

This layer enables to:

- Display the information of IWT and retroactive advice;
- Set scenario and launch simulation;
- Plan travel and choose timeslot;
- Establish a contract between the shipper and forwarder and provide a digital document.

Core entity

This layer consists of a set of algorithms; the result will feed the user layers throughout dedicated APIs. This layer is dedicated to data to assess the compliance with the requirement, optimize performance and mitigate the disturbances to reach resilience and sustainability.

According to the objectives of this LL which are described in the GA, this layer of DT may be structured into 4 modules. The module “Forecast and models” is common to all LLs, it concerns hydraulic modelling and methodological forecasting. The “Resilience analysis” module contains algorithms to analyse and evaluate resilience and sustainability based on suitable KPIs. The “Optimization” module will involve multiples objectives functions to improve operational performances according to the functional requirements. Based on the result of the optimization module, the “Mitigation” module will manage the mitigation solutions in case of disruption to preserve a maximum level of service.

Data connection and device control

This layer is in charge of performing two roles. On the one hand, it acquires sensor data and feed both the core entity layer and the user layer. On the other hand, it may transfer commands from the core entity or user interface to the devices in the real world. For example, we can imagine that IWT-DT control locks or pumps.

Figure 18: Functional & organic architecture of LL3.

4.6 Living Lab #4 Architectural Views

4.6.1 Functional view

Figure 19 describes the functional view for the DT dedicated to the LL4.

Figure 19: Functional architecture of LL4 (The CCNR is the exterior actor according to the GA).

User entity

Similar to other LLs, this layer presents a set of functionalities dedicated to the stakeholders and users. The interface layer contains the tools that enable the user to interact with the DT to display the information, set scenarios and launch simulation. It also establishes a smart contract between the shipper and forwarder and provides digital documents.

Core entity

The algorithms and analysis proposed in this layer are classified into three different classes: Simulation, optimisation and resilience analysis.

Data connection and device control

This layer on the one hand acquires sensor data and feed both the core entity layer and the user layer and on the other hand, can transfer commands from the core entity or user interface to the devices in the real world.

4.7 Global functional view of all the Living Labs

Based on the different usage, needs, requirements and the functional breakdown of each of the living lab, we can regroup the different visions into a single functional and organic framework that shows the common features and components shared between the living labs and their corresponding use cases as well as what makes them different. We can see in the Figure 20 the 3 functional layers and the organic one with functional assets in a specific colour for each living lab and some in grey for those that are cross-functional.

Figure 20: Global Functional View for the Living labs of ReNEW project.

5 Risk management

The purpose of the IWT resilience and sustainability framework is to ensure confidence in service and compliance with rules, in both short-term and long-term despite challenging conjectures and changing environment. This objective requires effective management of resources, a robust forecasting and prediction tools, and efficient risks management.

Resilience and sustainability assessment require that a hazards analysis be carried out to identify and evaluate the potential risks associated with climate change, poor service, scarcity and accident occurrence. The identified risks concern the infrastructure, the hydraulic aspect, the business, the employee, the environment, and the service. For example, If the water morphology is evaluated as critical through dedicated KPIs, an action should be taken to reduce the risks, smooth the effect and avoid breakdown point [7] [8].

Indeed, it is important to have a risk management approach dedicated to IWT [7]. For each identified risk, an assessment of criticality should be addressed by considering different attributes such as: the severity, the likelihood, the probability of occurrence, and the avoidance. This enables to assigning a score to the risks and classifying them by levels.

As depicted in Figure 21 and presented by [1], the risk management approach is organized into five depending stages:

- a. Identification of hazards: based on the resilience and sustainability objective, this stage aims to identify the hazards which threaten the most sensitive parts of the IWT system.
- b. Identification of potential risks: each identified hazard may induce different risks on the IWT, they require to be identified.
- c. Risks evaluation: this stage is dedicated to evaluate the impact and the degree of reversibility of the consequences caused to the users, the system, and the environment. A large spectrum of approaches, from simple to sophisticated, may be applied to classified risks. At this stage of the project, a risk matrix is used, it is suitable to come up with a preliminary evaluation et qualify a risk. The levels are as follows:
 - 1) Economic consequence and/or safety problem
 - 2) User jeopardized or/and environment strongly affected but reversible with light effort
 - 3) Danger of fatality and/or reversible damage to the environment but with important effort
 - 4) Entire system is threatened and/or the user may also be affected irreversibly.
- d. Risk estimation: the KPIs enable to capture the risks and their impact.

- e. Decision support and recommendations: this stage deal with mitigation actions and risk control.

Figure 21: Illustration of the risk management pipeline.

5.1 Hazard and risk scenarios

Table 3 below covers numerous use cases for IWT. For each use case, the above risk management pipeline is applied.

The result of this review of potential risks was that 60 functional, economic, environmental, and social impact categories have been identified. The priority and the interest of the scenarios depend on the objectives of each LL. However, the risk analysis enables to categorize the scenarios according to the specificities of each LL. As addressed Table 3 presents the KPIs which can be considered in the assessment of each scenario. Moreover, a set of potential mitigation actions are proposed.

Table 3: Detailed Risk Analysis Table.

Hazards & Threats	Potential risk	KPIS	Mitigation measures
Water scarcity	Risk to the business model from disruption to operational capacity	Mean time to detect a change Mean time to incidence discovery Tolerance Mean time to recover Profitability Cost inflation rate Return per vessel Number of operators Service level Market share Service loss Service cost	Reroute the vessels Adapt the vessel class Integrate another mode of transport in a section of a waterway Increase the number of modal shift areas Improve the water level and the width of the waterway by using fairway engineering structures Improve dredging service Predict the water scarcity occurrence Change container size
	Risk to the availability of waterway	Continuity Manoeuvrability Load capacity Water depth Deployment capacity Rerouting capacity Reassignment capacity ETA	Reroute the vessels Adapt the vessel class Shift to another mode of transport in a section of a waterway Redirect the water by using fairway engineering structures Improve dredging service Predict the water scarcity occurrence Manage waiting times well Warn operators

	Risk to the energy consumption	ETA Waiting time Load capacity Distance	Warn operators Adapt the class of vessel
	Risk to the service from reduced water depth	Water depth Load capacity Minimum fairway depth	Reroute the vessels Adapt the vessel class Shift to another mode of transport Redirect the water by using fairway engineering structures Improve dredging service Manage waiting times well Adapt waterway traffic and security signs Warn operators
	Risks to the vessel from low water level	Manoeuvrability Load capacity Class of the vessel Travel time Efficiency of the vessel Down time rate	Warn operators dredging the waterway bed Adapt waterway signs and marking Reroute the vessel Redirect the water by using fairway engineering structures
	Risks to the load capacity due to low water level	Load capacity Class of the vessel Minimum fairway depth	Adapt the vessel class Adapt the container size Increase the number of suitable vessels Reroute the vessels Redirect the water by using fairway engineering structures

	Risk to waterway accommodation capacity from low water level	Minimum water width Minimum water depth Pollution rate Class of allowed vessel	Adapt the vessel class Adapt the container size Increase the number of suitable vessels Redirect the water by using fairway engineering structures
	Risk to business activity from decreasing of load capacity	Profitability Cost inflation rate Efficiency of the vessel Number of operators Service level Market share Service loss Service cost	Adapt the vessel class Adapt the container size Increase the number of suitable vessels Redirect the water by using fairway engineering structures
Flooding	Risk to the business model	Service loss Tolerance Mean time to detect Mean time to forecast Rerouting capacity Mean down time Main time to recover Reassignment capacity Frequency of flood	Forecast the flood meteorological conditions Predict the flood Alert the population Alert the operators Establish emergency evacuation plans Prepare fire squads and police Dock the vessels Maintain the water drainage network in the city Maintain the water drainage network in the terminals Properly size drainage engineering structures Maintenance des infrastructures Rehabilitation of damaged infrastructures Protect storage areas Prepare floating electric generators

	<p>Risk on the availability of waterway</p>	<p>Service loss Tolerance Mean down time Main time to recover Reassignment capacity Water discharge Water level Bridge clearance Minimum high under the bridge Water velocity Identification of location Total flood area Width variation Duration</p>	<p>Forecast the flood meteorological conditions Predict the flood Alert the population Alert the operators Prepare water-draining equipment Anticipate needs</p>
	<p>Risk to the infrastructure health</p>	<p>Water discharge Water level Bridge clearance Minimum high under bridge Water velocity Identification of location Total flood area Width variation Mean time to detect Sedimentation index Erosion index Infrastructure's state Erosion state Duration</p>	<p>Alert the population Alert the operators Prepare fire squads and police Maintain the water drainage network in the city Maintain the water drainage network in the terminals Properly size drainage engineering structures Maintenance des infrastructures Rehabilitation of damaged infrastructures Build engineering structures to protect bank from erosion</p>

	Risk to the operator security	<p>Water discharge Water level Bridge clearance Minimum high beneath a bridge Water velocity Identification of location Total flood area Width variation Mean time to detect Sedimentation index Erosion index Infrastructure's state</p>	<p>Forecast the flood meteorological conditions Predict the flood Alert the population Alert the operators Establish emergency evacuation plans Prepare fire squads and police Dock the vessels</p>
	Risk to the service	<p>Water discharge Water level Bridge clearance Minimum high beneath a bridge Water velocity Identification of location Total flood area Width variation Mean time to detect Sedimentation index Erosion index Mean down time Mean time to recover</p>	<p>Alert the population Alert the operators Prepare fire squads and police Maintain the water drainage network in the city Maintain the water drainage network in the terminals Properly size drainage engineering structures Maintenance des infrastructures Rehabilitation of damaged infrastructures Build engineering structures to protect bank from erosion Dock the vessels Prepare floating electric generators</p>

Risk to the vessels from flooding	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Water discharge Water level Bridge clearance Minimum high under a bridge Water velocity Identification of location Total flood area Width variation Mean time to detect Sedimentation index Erosion index Infrastructure's state Duration 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Alert the population Alert the operators Prepare fire squads and police Maintain the water drainage network in the city Maintain the water drainage network in the terminals Properly size drainage engineering structures Maintain infrastructures Rehabilitation of damaged infrastructures Build engineering structures to protect bank from erosion Dock the vessels Prepare floating electric generators
Risk to the bridges from flooding	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Water discharge Water level Water velocity Identification of location Total flood area Sedimentation index Infrastructure's state Duration 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Alert the population Alert the operators Prepare fire squads and police Maintain the water drainage network in the city Maintain the water drainage network in the terminals Properly size drainage engineering structures Maintain infrastructures Restore damaged infrastructures Check the level of erosion Check the health state Suspend the bridge use
Risk on the waterway marking from flood	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Waterway marking state 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Restore waterway signs and marking

Heavy rainfall	Risk on the service from increased water flow	Water discharge Water level Bridge clearance Minimum high under a bridge Water velocity Identification of location Width variation Mean time to detect Manoeuvrability ETA	
	Risks to the vessels from high water level	Water discharge Water level Bridge clearance Minimum high under a bridge Water velocity Identification of location	
	Risk of flooding from heavy rainfall	Water discharge Water level Identification of location Width variation Mean time to detect Duration	
	Risk of Flash flooding	Water discharge Water level Identification of location Width variation Mean time to detect Duration	

	Risk of shore erosion from heavy rainfall	Water discharge Duration	
	Risk from water discharge to energy consumption	Energy consumption Water discharge	
Climate change	Risk to navigability from changing seasonality	Water discharge Water level Bridge clearance Minimum high under a bridge Water velocity Identification of location Width variation Manoeuvrability ETA Fairway depth Duration	Forecast seasonality Reroute the vessels Adapt the vessel class Shift to another mode of transport Redirect the water by using fairway engineering structures Improve dredging service Manage waiting times well Adapt waterway signs and marking Warn operators Anticipate the need

	Risk to the navigability from wind, fog and storm	Identification of location Manoeuvrability ETA Duration	Forecast weather Predict localisation Shift to another mode of transport Redirect the water by using fairway engineering structures Improve dredging service Manage waiting times well Warn operators Anticipate the need
	Risk to the employees from high temperature	Temperature Heatwave duration	Forecast weather Adapt timeslot work
	Risk to offshore port from storm and high waves	Identification of location Manoeuvrability Wind speed Duration	Forecast weather Predict localisation Build protecting engineering structures
	Risk to habitat from temperature increase	Habitat states (Observations) Temperature	Establish sanctuary Protect and restore habitat
	Risk to species from water scarcity	Habitat state (Observations) Species survey	Establish sanctuary Reintroduce species and check conservation

Conjuncture	Risks to business from scarcity of demand	Level of service Profitability Operational efficiency Return per vessel Service level Market share Service loss Service cost Duration	
	Risks to business from employees strike	Level of service Service loss Duration	
	Risks to business from unattractiveness of jobs and salaries	Average age of employees Job resignation rate Rate of open positions	
Poor Service	Risk to security from vessel behaviour and violate required speed	Vessel speed Vessel position Vessel class	Penalty invoice
	Risk to water quality from illegal dumping of sewage	Vessel position Testimony Level of sewage in the tank	Penalty invoice
	Risk to a vessel from disobeying approved path	Vessel speed Vessel position	Penalty invoice

	Risk to business from the railway and road competition	Service cost Average ETA Market share service loss Pollution index	Optimize level service Optimize service cost Increase the transport capacity Increase the service agility Reduce ETA Ensure the security of needs Provides high-service quality Reduce footprint carbon Optimize efficiency
	Risk to business from loading and unloading latency	Loading capacity Loading time Unloading capacity Unloading time Penalty due to delay	Reduce ETA Optimize load and unloading time Preserve the goods quality un/loading process
	Risk to finance, investment, and insurance	Level of service Profitability Return per vessel Market share Service loss Service cost Duration	Optimize Profitability Advertise Optimize security Increase service efficiency
	Risk of flooding from failure of infrastructure such as dam or lock	Infrastructure maintenance index	Maintain and rehabilitate infrastructures Monitor the health state Diagnosis failures

	Risk of travel and freight delay from poor planning	ETA Service level Rerouting capacity Reassignment capacity	Optimize planning Optimize service schedule Reroute vessels Distribute the load Forecast the seasonality Monitor the navigability Check the un/loading capacity
	Risk of power supply interruption from poor maintenance	Maintenance complying	Diagnosis failures Monitor health state Repair equipment
	Risk of smart service bug from poor update	Software updating index rate of bug	Verify software update before deployment
	Risk to business from unsynchronized intermodal shift	Transit time or transfer time Transfer capacity	Identify transfer capacity Identify and schedule timeslot for transfer
	Risk to service from lock failure	Waiting time Loss of service	Diagnosis failures Monitor health state Repair equipment Control the water transfer
	Risk to habitat from dredging	Habitat state	Control the depth and extent of dredging Preserve sections from dredging

6 Resilience and sustainability

IWT is characterized by interdependencies between heterogeneous elements and phenomena and is particularly exposed to the variation of the environment, to intermodal competition, and is characterized by different types of uncertainties. Moreover, on the one hand, it requires preserving economic, environmental, and social well-being in both short-term and long-term. On the other hand, it requires abilities to preserve and to recover the essential functionalities after and during disturbances. The ability of the IWT system to cope with faults, stress, disruption and disaster may be analysed under the concepts of resilience and sustainability. As explained by [9] and depicted in Figure 22, there are three paradigms:

The first Paradigm states that resilience is a subset of sustainability. In other words, strengthening the resilience of IWT system improves sustainability, but improving sustainability does not mean that the IWT system became more resilient. To reach sustainability, IWT must comply with the rules and be able to maintain economic and social development over time and space. In the literature, beside the resilience related metrics, those dedicated for sustainability focus more on economic, environmental and social aspects [9], [10].

According to [10] and [11], the resilience of the IWT system represents its ability to withstand unforeseen disruption, ensures a minimum level of service, remove structural weaknesses, and comply with security level, rules, and standards.

The second paradigm considers sustainability as a subset of resilience, which means that improving sustainability will increase resilience, but more resilience does not necessarily mean sustainability improvement.

The third paradigm is based on the decorrelation between resilience and sustainability, these two concepts can even be negatively correlated.

Figure 22: Different paradigms on the relation between Resilience and sustainability.

Assessing and evaluating resilience and sustainability over-time in such system is very challenging. The process implies having information, measurement, anticipation, detection, diagnosis, analysis of cascading effects, and feedback through decision-making. Therefore, it is important to define efficient metrics which are relevant for both resilience and sustainability.

6.1 Level of service

The resilience in IWT may be defined as the capacity to provide or maintain an acceptable level of service [11]. The ability of IWT to maintain the system’s functionality despite disturbance and disruption.

The system permeance is characterized by a boundary defined as the minimum level of service or the lowest acceptable level of performance.

It is possible to express resilience over the 3 different time phases with respect to challenges and faults (events) that threaten the normal level of service:

6.2 Resilience phases

As depicted in Figure 24, the resilience may be analysed through three distinct phases:

6.2.1 Preparation phase:

Metrics considered in this dimension measure the preparedness of the IWT system to deal with disruption and climate change.

6.2.2 Service Delivery phase:

Metrics in this dimension measure the difference in service level before, during and after the fault or challenge.

6.2.3 Recovery phase:

Metrics considered in this dimension concern how quickly a service can recover from disruption or fault.

Figure 23: Resilience phases.

7 Assessment and evaluation of resilience and sustainability

This approach presents 4 branches. The branch of IWT modelling enables us to identify the combination of metaphysical items that shape the IWT system. It highlights the available data, and it provides a more comprehensive view of how IWT parts interact and depend on each other. More details are provided in the section dealing with a functional view. The second branch illustrates the three phases of the resilience, primarily distinguished by pre-disturbance preparedness, service delivery post-disturbance, and recovery process. More details are given in section 6.2. The third branch contains four identified axes enabling to assess the resilience and sustainability: the monitoring, the withstanding, the absorptive, and the restorative capacities. The fourth branch addresses the capabilities which should characterize a resilient and sustainable IWT system. Based on the guidelines for better resilience and sustainability, a list of KPIs was chosen based on their intrinsic information and their consistency to evaluate the IWT capabilities. The methodology is based on collecting timely indicators to evaluate the resilience attributes at the local and global scale of the IWT system, also in the short term and in the long-term purposes.

Figure 24: Resilience and sustainability analysis.

7.1 Properties

7.1.1 Reliability

Reliability can be defined as the degree to which deliveries arrive on time, i.e., the percentage of shipments arriving on time in a certain time period (month, year). It is expected that low and high-water levels in waterways will result in an increase in the number of inland waterway deliveries that do not arrive on time

7.1.2 Robustness

Represent the minimum level of service achieved during the disruption scenario, in other words it represents the withstand capacity of the IWT system to face the stress without degradation of service.

7.1.3 Sensitivity

It represents the capacity to detect the event or factor affecting the IWT system and translate it to KPI variation.

7.1.4 Selectivity

The selectivity depicts the capacity to detect a change in the properties of the IWT system, localize it and isolate it. In other words, it is the ability to discriminate an effect.

7.1.5 Scalability

It represents the ability to extend operating capacity and handling growing activities and demand.

7.1.6 Adaptability

The adaptability describes the ability to analyse acceptable options, identifying alternative and elaborating plan.

7.1.7 Flexibility

The ability to take swift action in response to unforeseen events. It's an agility capability among other capabilities such as responsiveness

7.1.8 Agility

It represents the ability IWT system to respond quickly to changes in order to mitigate its impact if necessary.

7.1.9 Rapidity

It represents the quickness with which the system recovers after disturbance.

7.1.10 Resourcefulness

It represents the capacity to identify weaknesses, and mobilize resources (financial, human, technological).

7.1.11 Protectiveness

It depicts the capacity of constituents and infrastructures to protect from the unforeseen event and worst scenario

Table 4: Matching KPIs with resilience phases and properties.

Resilience dimensions		Resilience Phases			
Dimensions	Capabilities	Preparedness phase		Service delivery phase	Recovery phase
Monitoring		KPI		KPI	KPI
Sensitivity	Sensitivity	Mean time to detect change	Economics:	Infrastructures state	Mean down time
		Mean time to detect variation	Inflation rate	Mean time between failures	Rerouting capacity
		Mean time to forecast change	Market share		Mean time to recover
		Rate of on time delivery	Profitability		Reassignment capacity
		Mean time to incident discovery	Number of operators		
		Security audit efficiency	Median/ average age of employees		
		Risk assessment			
		Tolerance	Operation:		
		Budget deviation	Load capacity per fleet		
		Vessel related Sensitivity incidents	Loading and unloading capacity per crane		
			Occupancy		
		Ecological:	EIA		
		Foot print carbon	Percentage of downtime		
		Habitat status	Equipment failures rate		
		Pollution rate	Vessels positions		
			Critical area localization		
		Social:	waiting time		
		Overtime hours	Localization of congestion		
		Employee satisfaction rate	Number of rerouting solutions		
			Number of alternative transport modes		
		Hydraulics:			
		Water discharge			
		Water level	Navigation:		
		Water level variation	Continuity		
			Collision risk		
		Infrastructure	Manoeuvrability index		
		Erosion state	Water level		
		Sedimentation state (quantification)	Waterway Depth		
		Drainage and conveyance capacity	Waterway Width		
		State of structures	Bridge clearance		
Material fatigue (based life cycle)					
Navigation signs					
Selectivity	Selectivity	Detection and localization of degradation		Detection and localization of failure	Mean time to repair
		Water level which affects navigability and load capacity		Mean time to detect failure	Mean time to recover

		Meteorological data to forecast storm and duration, which can cause flooding or navigation disturbance and damages ecosystem		Mean time to detect disruption	
		Meteorological data to forecast drought and its affected area		RUL: remaining useful life (Operational availability)	
		Mean time to detect state change			
		Mean time to recognize a source of disruption			
Withstanding					
	Resistance			Operational mean time between failures	
				Delay variation	
	Safety & Security	Risk assessment coverage		Damage cost	
		Safety and security audit		Incident rate	
		Infrastructure and equipment		Mean time to evacuate	
		Rescue capacity			
		Emergency evacuation capacity			
	Efficiency			Operational reliability	Mean time to incident recover
				Operational availability	Mean down time
				Mean time to intervene	
				Mean time evacuate	
	Robustness			Service loss	Mean time to incident recover
				Level of service (minimum level of service)	Mean down time
				Capacities	
				Response time	
				ETA	
				Degradation rate	
				Degradation	
				Duration of degradation	
	Availability			Response time	
				Operational availability	
				Duration of degradation	
				Minimum level of service	
	Coordination	Coordination Budget		Response time	
				Mean time to intervene	
				Mean time to adjust	
				Mean time evacuate	
				Cost of coordination	
	Protectiveness	Capacity to absorb flood		Rate of unforeseen events	Aftershock capacities
		Capacity to mitigate drought		Rate of TP, TN, FP, FN prediction	
		Water quality indicator			
		Pollution quality indicator			
		Mean time to deploy support			

Absorptive	Cascading Failure			Spread rate	Recovery rate
					Mean time to incident recover
					Mean down time
	Resourcefulness			Recovery rate	
Fragility				Rate of immobilized resources (human, material, financial)	Deviation from nominal value
				Maximum capacity	Mean down time
				Minimum capacity	
				Operational thresholds	
Scalability				Critical thresholds	
				Mean time to connect with intermodal transportation	Mean time to connect with intermodal transportation
				Capacity of transfer to intermodal transport	Capacity of transfer to intermodal transport
Restorative					
	Operational flexibility			Response time to incident or disturbance	
	Resourcefulness			Rate of immobilized resources (human, material, financial)	
Stability	Service level			EIA variance	Market share variance
				Load capacity variance	
				Pollution variance	Number of vessels variance
				Seasonality variance	Load and storage capacity variance
				Number of species variance	
				Delay variation	
Rapidly				Time to arrive	Mean time to recover
				Delay variation	Mean time to maintain
					Mean time to intervene
					Mean down time
Agility (Adaptability)				Response time to incident or disturbance	
				Response time to service demand	
Maintainability				Mean time to repair	Mean time to recover

7.2 KPIs and description

This section describes the calculation and/or the measurement of above KPIs by providing their definition, corresponding unit, and getting method. We clusterise these KPIs according to different perspectives. Different important aspects that can affect the sustainability and resilience of IWT have been considered, such as ecological, social, economic, hydraulics, infrastructure, quality of service, navigability, rules, climate, and maintenance. In the next update of this deliverable, we will match these KPIs with each LL and highlight those that are in common.

Table 5: KPI description

KPI name	Full name of the KPI
Acronym	Term used to assign the KPI or the indicator
Type	Indicate the type of the data: Real, Boolean, String, ...
Unit	Indicates the measurement unit, percentage, no unit...
Description	Description of the KPI/ measure/ indicator
Objective	Describes the expected purposes through this indicator Indicate the added-value of this indicator
Measurement method	Describe the formula enabling to calculate the indicator or how to acquire the measure whether is directedly provided by sensors or systems
Frequency	Represents the number of samples per period, or the number of refreshes per time period
Safe limit	The operating limit may be considered as the nominal interval the interval in which the system should ideally operate. But the safe limits for each entity in the IWT must be defined later. At a safe limit, there is not yet an emergency situation, but it implies actions to bring the behaviour back into the nominal range. Beyond the safe limits, there are emergency limits. If the measurement rises over emergency limits, an immediate action is required.
Reporting format	Describes how to display the information through chart, text, etc
Sources	Sources providing the data to calculate the indicator

7.2.1 Sustainability

Ecological

Footprint carbon

KPI name	Footprint carbon
Acronym	
Type	Real
Unit	Tons of carbon dioxide equivalent (tCO ₂ e)
Description	The annual amount of greenhouse gas (GHG) that was produced as a result of IWT activities. All the GHGs are expressed in terms of carbon dioxide equivalent.
Objectives	Enable to: Assess the eco-friendliness of the IWT system and the compliance with the rules.
Formula	It depends on the activity, the engines, the fuel, the stream direction, the load, etc
Sources	Engines information, engine speed, loading status, operational data, navigation data, fuel consumption sensors

Habitat status

KPI name	Habitat status
Acronym	
Type	String
Unit	Level or percentage
Description	It indicates the health of the habitat and the species conservation status
Objectives	It enables to assess the habitat conservation or deterioration
Formula	Observation
Sources	Experts, water quality, air quality, temperature, dragging rate

Water quality

KPI name	Water quality
Acronym	
Type	string
Unit	Ph, DO, Turbidity, etc
Description	It describes the condition of water in terms of pollutants and toxicity regarding the habitat, drinking, or swimming.
Objectives	Assess the quality of water and the habitat conservation
Formula	measurement
Sources	Dedicated sensors, observation

Air quality index

KPI name	Air quality index
Acronym	AQI
Type	Real
Unit	µg/m ³
Description	Air pollution indicator. It measures the pollution caused by the vessels. Numerous gas may be considered, such as Nitrogen Dioxide (NO ₂), Sulphur Dioxide (SO ₂), Ozone (O ₃), Carbon Dioxide (CO ₂) and Carbon Monoxide (CO)
Objectives	Monitor the quality of air along the waterway
Formula	Measurement
Sources	Pollution sensors. However, in this project ICCS can deliver the sensors

Social

Rate of overtime hours

KPI name	Rate of overtime hours
Acronym	
Type	Real
Unit	[%]
Description	It represents the time worked beyond the contractual slot.
Objectives	Enable to assess: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Service efficiency • Employee wellbeing
Formula	$\frac{\text{Overtime hours}}{\text{Contractual hours}}$
Sources	Operator, IWT authority

Employee satisfaction rate

KPI name	Employee satisfaction rate
Acronym	
Type	Integer or string
Unit	scale
Description	It describes whether the employee concerns are addressed at work
Objectives	Enable to assess employee wellbeing
Formula	Survey
Sources	Operators, IWT authority, labour inspection

Economical

Budget deviation

KPI name	Budget deviation
Acronym	
Type	Real
Unit	[%]
Description	It represents the deviation from the initial approved budget.
Objectives	Enable to: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Assess the compliance with the budget for maintenance and rehabilitation. Assess the quality of the service.
Formula	$\frac{\sum_i(\text{deviated budget} - \text{approved budget})}{\text{approved budget}}$
Sources	Operators, IWT authority

Inflation rate

KPI name	Inflation rate
Acronym	
Type	real
Unit	[%]
Description	Prices per distance or prices per load increase over time
Objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Assess the economic attractiveness. Assess price stability. Assess the competitiveness.
Formula	$\frac{\text{price}_{t+1} - \text{price}_t}{\text{price}_t}$
Sources	Operators, IWT authority, financial authority.

Market share

KPI name	Market share
Acronym	
Type	Real
Unit	[%]
Description	Volume activity of IWT regarding the overall logistics activity
Objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Assess the economic attractiveness Assess the competitiveness Assess the growth (expenses)
Formula	$\frac{\text{IWT logistic activity}}{\text{Total logistic activity}}$
Sources	Operators, IWT authority, financial authority

Profitability

KPI name	Profitability
Acronym	
Type	Real
Unit	Euros
Description	Gross profit margin. It represents the extent to which IWT companies earn a profit.
Objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Assess the financial success Asses the good financial health Assess the competitiveness
Formula	operating margin = gross profit – operating costs
Sources	Operators, IWT authority, financial authority

Profitability variance

KPI name	Profitability variance
Acronym	
Type	Real
Unit	
Description	Spread in profit
Objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Assess the stability of profit Assess the financial sustainability Assess the economic attractiveness Assess the competitiveness
Formula	$\sqrt{\frac{\sum_i(x_i - mean)}{n - 1}}$
Sources	Operators, IWT authority, financial authority

Number of operators

KPI name	Number of operators
Acronym	
Type	Integer
Unit	
Description	The number of companies operating in IWT
Objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Assess the economic attractiveness Assess the competitiveness Assess the growth (expenses) Assess the health of the business
Formula	Count of operators
Sources	IWT authority

Average age of employee

KPI name	Average age of employee
Acronym	

Type	Real
Unit	year
Description	Median age of the labour force
Objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Assess the attractiveness Assess the competitiveness Assess the growth (expenses)
Formula	
Sources	IWT authority, operators

7.2.2 Resilience

Hydraulic

Water discharge (flow)

KPI name	Water discharge (flow)
Acronym	Q
Type	Real
Unit	[l/s] or [m ³ /s]
Description	Volumetric amount of water carried per unit time
Objectives	Enables to: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Assess strength of the stream Asses the navigability Predict a potential flooding Assess the security of infrastructures and users
Formula	$\frac{Volume}{Time}$
Sources	Flow sensors

Water level

KPI name	Water level
Acronym	
Type	Real
Unit	[m]
Description	High of water in the waterway
Objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Assess the navigability Assess the drought Assess the continuity of waterway Assess the load capacity Bridge clearance Assess the manoeuvrability of vessels Assess the classes of vessels to deploy Assess the number of vessels to deploy

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Assess the service loss Asses the service level Assess the waterway availability Plan dragging Asses the habitat conservation
Formula	Measurement
Sources	Level gauge

Water level variation

KPI name	Water level variation
Acronym	
Type	Real
Unit	[%]
Description	
Objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Assess the stability of waterway and navigability Assess the uncertainties of navigability Assess the confidence in the water level
Formula	$\frac{\text{Current level}}{\text{Previous level at } (d - 1 \text{ or } w - 1)}$
Sources	Level gauge

Probable maximum

KPI name	Probable Maximum Flood
Acronym	PMF
Type	Real
Unit	
Description	The largest level of flood that could occur at a particular location.
Objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Assess the stability of waterway and navigability Assess the uncertainties of navigability Assess the confidence in the water level Assess the safety of users Anticipate a mitigation action Anticipate emergency plan
Formula	Estimation
Sources	Weather services

Infrastructures

Erosion state

KPI name	Erosion state
Acronym	
Type	String or real

Unit	[%], scale or [m]
Description	Over the time, the water removes soil and material. The intensity depends on the type of material and the water flow.
Objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Assess the removed soil or the dissolved material. Plan maintenance and rehabilitation. Warn about a potential hazard.
Formula	Previous boundary – Current boundary
Sources	Expert, observation or camera processing

Sedimentation state (quantification)

KPI name	Sedimentation state (quantification)
Acronym	
Type	Real
Unit	[m], [m2], or [m3]
Description	Deposition of sand or material on the waterway bed
Objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Assess the waterway depth Plan maintenance Asses the loading capacity Warn about critical areas Plan dragging work Bathymetric survey Sedimentation monitoring
Formula	Measurements
Sources	Bathymetry devices (sonar and radar)

Drainage and conveyance capacity

KPI name	Drainage and conveyance capacity
Acronym	
Type	Real
Unit	[m3/S]
Description	Amount of water that can be discharged by the terminal gutters and waterway
Objectives	Assess a potential flooding
Formula	$\frac{\text{Water volume}}{\text{Time}}$
Sources	IWT authority, terminal authority, sizing information

State of structures

KPI name	State of structures
Acronym	
Type	Real or string
Unit	Level of service or operational status
Description	Amount of water that can be discharged by the terminal gutters and waterway

Objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Assess the availability • Assess the occupancy • Estimate the waiting time • Assess the level of service • Assess service lost • Estimate actual service capacity • Estimate the time to recover • Plan maintenance • Seek for alternative
Formula	It depends on the type of infrastructure
Sources	Sensors, observation

Material fatigue

KPI name	Material fatigue
Acronym	
Type	Real
Unit	
Description	Cracks due to stress
Objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Plan maintenance • Avoid breakdown • Avoid hazard • Improve the level of service
Formula	Diagnosis, measurement, and observation
Sources	Operators, sensors

Navigation signs

KPI name	Navigation signs
Acronym	
Type	
Unit	
Description	Traffic signs and marks which provide information to skipper.
Objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increase security • Avoid critical area
Formula	Observation
Sources	Observation

Service

Mean time to forecast change

KPI name	Mean time to forecast change
Acronym	MTFC
Type	Real

Unit	[s]
Description	The average time elapsed between a change prediction and its real occurrence.
Objectives	Evaluates the prediction module's ability to detect and estimate system state changes before they occur.
Formula	$\frac{\sum_i(\text{Occurrence time} - \text{prediction time})}{\text{Nbr of predicted events}}$
Sources	Output of forecasting modules and states measurements and observations of the IWT system.

Mean time to detect a change

KPI name	Mean time to detect a change
Acronym	MTTC
Type	Real
Unit	[s]
Description	The average time elapsed between the change of state and its detection. It characterizes the sensitivity of monitoring.
Objectives	Enable to assess: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The efficiency of the monitoring • Preparedness and responsiveness • The rapidity of detecting the state change in IWT components.
Formula	$\text{MTTC} = \frac{\sum_i(\text{Detection time} - \text{occurrence time})}{\text{Nbr of states change}}$
Sources	Sensors, Forecasting models, and observation

Tolerance

KPI name	Tolerance
Acronym	
Type	Real
Unit	[°],[m3],[ton],[%],etc
Description	Maximum operating capacity. Furthermore, it may be considered as the derivative marring regarding nominal operational value.
Objectives	It enables the assessment of: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The capacity of mooring in the port • The capacity to accommodate vessels in the waterway before causing congestion • The volumetric water capacity of the waterway • Etc.
Formula	
Sources	Sensors and information about the sizing of the IWT system.

Load capacity

KPI name	Load capacity
Acronym	

Type	Real
Unit	[t]
Description	The maximum allowed load. Overall, it depends on the water level and the classes of the vessel.
Objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Estimate the amount of goods and materials that the vessel can be carried. • Assess the service level. • Improve planning.
Formula	Calculated by benchmark
Sources	Level of water, class of vessel, benchmark

Loading and unloading capacity per crane

KPI name	Loading and unloading capacity per crane (Transit or transfer capacity)
Acronym	
Type	Real
Unit	[t/h]
Description	Amount of goods or material loaded by the crane over time
Objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Assess the level of service • Estimate the transit time • Estimate the waiting time
Formula	$\frac{\text{load transfer}}{\text{time}}$
Sources	Terminal authority, terminal operator, crane capacity information (from manufacturer datasheet)

Occupancy

KPI name	Occupancy
Acronym	
Type	Real
Unit	[%]
Description	The percent of used capacity
Objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Assess the service loss • Assess service level • Detect problems
Formula	$\frac{\text{operational capacity}}{\text{total capacity}}$
Sources	Operators

Estimated time of arrival

KPI name	Estimated time of arrival
Acronym	ETA
Type	Real
Unit	[s]
Description	The time when the vessel is expected to arrive at its destination

Objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Assess the rapidity Assess the quality of service Assess the traffic fluidity
Formula	$current\ ime + \frac{distance}{average\ speed\ of\ a\ vessel}$
Sources	Vessel sensors

Percentage of downtime

KPI name	Percentage of downtime
Acronym	
Type	Real
Unit	[%]
Description	Percent of time during which equipment, infrastructure, or part of the IWT system is unavailable for use.
Objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Asses loss of service Assess service level Plan maintenance Assess service quality Time to recover
Formula	$\frac{downtime}{working\ time}$
Sources	Operators, diagnosis, sensors

Equipment failures rate

KPI name	Equipment failures rate
Acronym	
Type	Real
Unit	Fail/[day]
Description	The frequency with which equipment fails.
Objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Asses the service level Estimate maintenance budget
Formula	$\frac{Nbr\ of\ fails}{Time}$
Sources	Sensors, operators, observation

Vessels positions

KPI name	Vessels positions
Acronym	
Type	Real
Unit	[m]
Description	Vessel location and coordinates in real time
Objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Assess the compliance of the vessel with the approved path Assess the traffic Monitor the travel

Formula	Measurement
Sources	AIS

Critical area localization

KPI name	Critical area localization
Acronym	
Type	Real
Unit	Coordinates
Description	Area presenting a hazard to vessels and users. For example, an area where there is a sandbank requires to be warned.
Objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Warn vessel Reroute the vessels Plan dragging
Formula	Observation
Sources	Operators

Waiting time

KPI name	Waiting time
Acronym	
Type	Real
Unit	[s]
Description	Time elapsed between stop and restart during travel
Objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Estimate the ETA Assess the rapidity The quality of service Assess the fluidity Manage the planning
Formula	Measurement
Sources	Vessel sensors

Localization of congestion

KPI name	Localization of congestion
Acronym	
Type	
Unit	
Description	Decrease of vessel velocity when the number of vessels at some area is larger than the waterway or lock capacity.
Objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Assess the traffic fluidity Assess the level of service Estimate the waiting time Plan mitigation action Plan maintenance
Formula	Measurement, observation

Sources	Vessel sensors, AIS
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Number of rerouting solutions

KPI name	Number of rerouting solutions
Acronym	
Type	Integer
Unit	
Description	It represents the modification of the path to reach a destination or a suitable alternative destination.
Objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Assess the ability to get around an obstruction Assess the capacity to mitigate disturbance
Formula	Path change and
Sources	Water level, waterway size, terminal capacity, vessel class

Number of alternative transport modes

KPI name	Number of alternative transport modes
Acronym	
Type	
Unit	
Description	Identification of the shifting modal area
Objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Assess the alternative solution
Formula	
Sources	

Rerouting capacity

KPI name	Rerouting capacity
Acronym	
Type	Integer
Unit	
Description	Modification of the path to reach the destination or a suitable alternative destination.
Objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Assess the ability to get around an obstruction Assess the capacity to mitigate disturbance
Formula	To be developed later
Sources	Water level, waterway size, terminal capacity, vessel class

Reassignment capacity

KPI name	Reassignment capacity
Acronym	
Type	Real
Unit	
Description	The ability to change the class of vessel, terminal, or transport mode to fix logistic issues

Objectives	Assess the ability to overcome a problem Assess the capacity to mitigate disturbance
Formula	To be developed later
Sources	Water level, waterway size, terminal mooring capacity, vessel class, modal shift

Rate of on-time delivery

KPI name	Rate of on-time delivery
Acronym	OTD
Type	Real
Unit	[%]
Description	This abdicator plays an important role in customer satisfaction. It represents the ability of operators to keep their commitments to customers.
Objectives	Enable to assess: -The confidence and efficiency of the system. -The service quality.
Formula	$\frac{\text{Total number of deliveries}}{\text{Nbr of late deliveries}}$
Sources	Operators, AIS tracking, IWT authority, planning system.

Navigation

Continuity

KPI name	Continuity
Acronym	
Type	Real or string
Unit	
Description	Navigation path is free of obstacles and a minimum navigation level satisfied. However, it depends on the load and the vessel class.
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Objectives 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Assess the navigability Assess the drought Assess the waterway availability Plan dragging Plan rehabilitation and maintenance
Formula	Waterway status
Sources	Water level, waterway information, bathymetric sensors

Collision risk

KPI name	Collision risk
Acronym	
Type	Integer or string
Unit	Level of risk
Description	It represents the possibility of colliding with vessels or infrastructures.

Objectives	Assess the manoeuvrability Warn the operators about a risk
Formula	
Sources	Water level, water flow, wind

Manoeuvrability index

KPI name	Maneuverability index
Acronym	
Type	Real
Unit	
Description	Controllability of the vessel in safe way
Objectives	Asses the controllability of the vessel Assess the collision risk
Formula	
Sources	Water level, water flow, wind, rudder state

Water level

KPI name	Maneuverability index
Acronym	
Type	Real
Unit	[m]
Description	High of water in the waterway
Objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Assess the navigability Assess the drought Assess the continuity of waterway Assess the load capacity Bridge clearance Assess the manoeuvrability of vessels Assess the classes of vessels to deploy Assess the number of vessels to deploy Assess the service loss and service level Assess the waterway availability Plan dragging Assess the habitat conservation
Formula	
Sources	Level gauge

Fairway Depth

KPI name	Fairway Depth
Acronym	
Type	Real
Unit	[m]
Description	The height between the water level and the riverbed, it does not necessary coincide with the water level.

Objectives	Assess load capacity Estimate the vessel's total draught Estimate keel clearance
Formula	Keel clearance + total draught, or with bathymetric measurement
Sources	Bathymetric sensors

Waterway Width

KPI name	Waterway width
Acronym	
Type	Real
Unit	[m]
Description	Cross section of waterway that corresponds to waterway depth
Objectives	Assess the class of vessel to deploy Assess the safety of navigation
Formula	
Sources	Bathymetric sensors

Bridge clearance

KPI name	Bridge clearance
Acronym	
Type	Real
Unit	[m]
Description	The vertical distance between the water line and part of a bridge that corresponds to the fairway width
Objectives	Assess the class of vessel to deploy Assess the safety of navigation Assess the navigability under a bridge Estimate the air draught of the vessel
Formula	
Sources	Water level, fairway width, bridge information

Rules

Illegal spills

KPI name	Illegal spills
Acronym	
Type	string
Unit	
Description	Dumping sewage illegally instead of using the appropriate collector
Objectives	Assess the compliance with the sewage rule Monitor the environmental protection
Formula	Observation
Sources	Observation, witness, camera, vessel position

Number of speed violation

KPI name	Number of speed violation
Acronym	
Type	Integer
Unit	
Description	Vessel speeding beyond the authorized limit
Objectives	Assess the compliance with the rules Monitor the traffic security
Formula	measurement
Sources	AIS, vessel velocity sensor

Path violation

KPI name	Path violation
Acronym	
Type	Real
Unit	
Description	Vessel Position outside the authorized path
Objectives	Assess the compliance with the approved path Monitor the traffic security Manage the traffic
Formula	
Sources	AIS

Security audit efficiency

KPI name	Security audit efficiency
Acronym	
Type	Integer or string
Unit	
Description	This KPI addresses how personnel, user, and vessels are protected.
Objectives	Enable to: Diagnosis security problems Assess the security procedures
Formula	Audit
Sources	Data about accidents, injuries, and harms.

Risk assessment

KPI name	Risk assessment
Acronym	RA
Type	Integer or string
Unit	SIL (Safety Integrity Level)
Description	Identification of potential hazards and level of risk
Objectives	It enables to:

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Assess The safety system performance • Prevents and mitigates the hazard • Look for vulnerabilities
Formula	See standard EN61508 and the annex of this deliverable
Sources	Historical data and forecasting data

Security audit efficiency

KPI name	Security audit efficiency
Acronym	
Type	Integer or string
Unit	
Description	This KPI addresses how personnel, user, and vessels are protected.
Objectives	Enable to: Diagnosis security problems Assess the security procedures
Formula	Audit
Sources	Data about accidents, injuries, and harms.

Climate

Seasonality variance

KPI name	Seasonality variance
Acronym	
Type	Real
Unit	
Description	Seasonality over the years changes in terms of time slot and intensity
Objectives	Assess the climate change Assess the navigability Estimate the time slot of waterway operability Anticipate mitigation actions
Formula	Measurements
Sources	Metrological data

Probable maximum precipitation

KPI name	probable maximum precipitation
Acronym	PMP
Type	Real
Unit	
Description	Estimation of a quantity of precipitation for a given duration a at specific location
Objectives	Assess the water flow of the waterway Assess the navigability Estimate the probability of flood

	Anticipate mitigation actions
Formula	Measurements and estimations
Sources	Metrological data

Maintenance

Mean Time to Incidence Discovery

KPI name	Mean Time to incidence Discovery
Acronym	MTTD
Type	Real
Unit	HH:MM:SS
Description	The average time elapsed between the appearance of an incident and its detection. It characterizes the efficiency and quality of system monitoring.
Objective	Enable to assess: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The rapidity in detecting an incident • The efficiency of the monitoring • It may help to improve the response time
Formula	$MTTID = \frac{\sum_i(Dicovry\ time - occurrence\ time)}{Nbr\ of\ incidents}$
Frequency	Daily, weekly, quarterly, annually
Target values	Thresholds to define
Reporting format	Distribution/time
Sources	Sources providing the data to calculate the indicator

Mean down time

KPI name	Mean down time
Acronym	
Type	Real
Unit	
Description	The mean time during which equipment, infrastructure, or part of the IWT system is unavailable for use.
Objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Assess loss of service Assess service level Plan maintenance Assess service quality Time to recover Assess the reliability
Formula	$\frac{\sum_i^n downtime}{n}$
Sources	Operators, diagnosis, sensors

Main time to recover

KPI name	Main time to recover
Acronym	MTTR
Type	Real
Unit	[s] or [h]
Description	Mean time that the IWT system takes to become fully operational after disturbance or failures.
Objectives	Assess the reactivity Assess the resilience
Formula	$\frac{\text{total downtime}}{\text{number of interventions}}$
Sources	Equipment status, operators

Main time to resolve

KPI name	Main time to resolve
Acronym	MTTR
Type	Real
Unit	[s] or [h]
Description	Mean time that the IWT system takes to resolve issues.
Objectives	Assess the reactivity Assess the resilience Assess a client's satisfaction Improve performance
Formula	$\frac{\text{Spent time to fixe incident}}{\text{number of incidence}}$
Sources	Equipment status, operators

Remaining useful life (battery)

KPI name	Remaining useful life (battery)
Acronym	RUL
Type	Real
Unit	
Description	Estimation of battery health and its level of degradation. This indicator is suitable for X-barge and floating battery use cases.
Objectives	Enable to assess:
Formula	Several approaches (model-based, data-based) or measurement
Sources	Battery sensors

Main time to failure

KPI name	Main time to failure
Acronym	MTTF
Type	Real
Unit	[s] or [h]

Description	Mean time between non-repairable failures in IWT system equipment
Objectives	Assess the quality of equipment and infrastructure Assess the service quality
Formula	$\frac{\text{Total operating time}}{\text{Number of equipment}}$
Sources	Equipment status, operators

Mean time between Failures

KPI name	Mean time between Failures
Acronym	MTBF
Type	Real
Unit	[s]
Description	The main time between repairable failures.
Objectives	Assess the reliability Assess the service confidence
Formula	
Sources	Equipment status, operators

Infrastructure state

KPI name	Infrastructure state
Acronym	
Type	String
Unit	
Description	Information about the current operating status of a device or infrastructure
Objectives	Assess the availability Assess the level of service Assess readiness to perform
Formula	Measurement or observation
Sources	Sensors, observation, and operators

Emergency evacuation capacity

KPI name	Emergency evacuation capacity
Acronym	
Type	Real
Unit	[Person/min]
Description	The number of persons to move per minute from a critical to a safe area
Objectives	Assess the emergency plan Anticipate evacuation facilities Manage fire squad deployment Assess the security of people
Formula	Sizing information
Sources	IWT authority, operators

8 Mitigation actions and alternative strategies

In this section, we present an overview of all the mitigation strategies and alternatives to support the resilience and sustainability. These strategies can range from a simple rule to something more elaborated. It is important to notice that the support decision making process need to consider these mitigation actions and strategies as a whole with the aim to establish the best action or sequence of actions to deploy in order to guarantee the resilience and sustainability of the system.

From the GA and the LL Workshops, we have identified the following mitigation actions and strategies:

Re-planning vessel trips

Through this mitigation action, in a collaborative way, shippers can do planning trips of inland waterway transportation fleet and can act in real-time in case of disruptions and request timeslots for transshipment (loading or discharging) at terminals. On the other side, Terminal operators can accept or refuse these requests. The information is updated by the skippers by adjusting continuously the estimated time of arrival (ETA).

From the data point of view, this route planner will be fed by different sources: Clearance heights, water levels, shipping notices, bridge operating time. In addition to the operation information about the occupancy rate of mooring and waiting times at locks. Much effort will be done in the fusion and consolidation of such static and dynamic data in order to be interoperable with the underlying planner.

Enhanced disruption information

Based on advanced AI-based models, the decision support tool will enrich the information about disruptions and waterways status with predictive information. This covers the estimated duration of the disruption and its impact on the time of arrival.

In addition, thanks to the knowledge graphs, we will be able to measure the impact of the disruption and forecast its propagation over the entire transportation network.

This information will be provided in real time and is supposed to improve the anticipation of complex situations for better planning.

Synchromodality in transportation hub

By using modular inter-modality platforms, the synchromodality and the transport of cargo and passengers are guaranteed. This allows transferring passengers from the river to the railway and

vice-versa, allowing for alternative solutions in case of prolonged damage on infrastructure (locks ...) or weather extreme events (low or high-water level ...).

Emergency plan

If the public network (gas, electricity.) fails due to extreme weather conditions, the newly developed ships in LL1 can serve as a "sailing battery" and can be used in the most urgent situations (power supply for the MCC, hospitals, police terminals,). As part of the concept, we also want to design a completely closed off-grid system, in which energy from solar panels and wind turbines can be stored at a small scale.

Infrastructure resource optimization

These mitigation actions aim to make IWT infrastructure more resilient to extreme events. The navigation locks, groynes and narrow fairway can be considered. For that purpose, we can for instance improve dredging service, widen narrow passages of the river, renew the infrastructure with the help of automated systems such as lock and moveable bridge, automation in terminals and ports with mooring and cargo handling, etc. ...

In addition to autonomous systems such as ships, and innovative assistance modular platform and pontoons, providing flow dispatching when the inland waterway is blocked or not navigable.

Penalisation and dissuasion mechanisms for wastewater deposits

The objective of this action is to promote healthy ecological behaviour and improve the sustainability of the river. It is following a contract between the river authority and the vessel owner to respect all the defined rules regarding the waste deposit in the river. Once any illegal wastewater deposit is detected, the penalties will be applied.

We describe below the mitigations strategies and alternatives that we might deploy regarding some identified hazard and threat scenarios (see Deliverable D1.1):

9 Unified View of Methodological Framework for Resilient and Sustainable IWT System

One of the key challenges in the Renew Project is how to provide a unified view of the digital twin solution able to respond at the most need and requirement of the living labs and uses cases in terms of resilience and sustainability.

The previous breakdown of the IWT system architecture helps us to mutualize features functionality and the compositional component of the targeted digital solutions.

The functional view presented in Figure 20 illustrates this convergence and also the specificity of the living lab when dealing with extreme events related to climate change and their corresponding risks, threats, and vulnerability that they can bring on traffic, infrastructure, flows, etc.

From the point of view of the logical components and interfaces, we could break down this function view into 4 layers as shown in Figure 25:

Physical twin: regroups all the physical components and the entities of the real world.

Technology: collections of different spaces, where the data is ingested (data space), the real-world entities are emulated/simulated, and certain activities and phenomena are forecasted with the help of AI models, and knowledge are stored to help the reasoning on similar contexts and situations if they are encountered.

Decision-making support: carry out the decisions and the strategies to deploy based on the adapted mitigation actions and with respect to constraints, requirements and sustainable and resilient KPIs to reach or to prioritize.

Supervision and Recommendation is the portal of the digital twin where the KPIs are translated into business, quantitative and qualitative indicators, and where the end-user could interact by choosing the what-if scenario to test and show the strategic rules and alternative to deploy.

Starting from the physical twin, data are collected and ingested into the data space in order to expose and organize them for their exploitation by the different other technological assets belonging to simulation, artificial intelligence or even blockchain (in the case of Doro's living lab use case).

From the point of view of the inland waterway manager, he/she could select and test a what-if scenarios related to the climate changes and including threats, hazards, vulnerabilities and risk scenarios.

Once the scenario is selected, the setting up of this scenario is done in order to introduce its parameters and factors in the different spaces/ technological assets. For instance, if we take the case of a food scenario, we will introduce the parameter of rainfall in the simulation models in order to update the water level of the river or a segment of the river if it is localized. In the same manner, this information is important if we want to update the prediction of the AI models based on the dynamic of the weather conditions during the last short period in order to predict the mid-term conditions.

This setting up will also be considered in the knowledge graph by integrating the infrastructure-based scenarios for example when a part of the river becomes inaccessible due to landslide obstruction. With the help of a knowledge graph and probabilistic models (Bayesian Networks, Markov Chain Models...), we will be able to characterize the status of the IWT at a whole and reasoning on the cause-and-effect of this scenario on the transportation network covering its infrastructure, traffic, passenger flow, etc.

Comes then the decision-support-making layer with the role of establishing mitigation and alternative solutions in order to absorb the impact and reduce their effects: depending on the living labs, we will find different assets that look to regulate the traffic by re-planning the vessel fleet, assign floating platforms or pontoons where we can evacuate people and take them by the emergency care or tranship cargos and goods to other transport modes. The assessment of these mitigation and alternative actions with the catalogue of resilient and sustainable KPIs enables scoring and ranking each action or solution according to these two dimensions in addition to the respect of identified environmental constraints related to the biodiversity of the species and their habitat in the underlying living lab.

Once this evaluation and ranking are done, the elaborated mitigation actions are presented to the IWTS Manager with the corresponding quantitative and qualitative KPIs. Thereby, the IWT crisis manager chooses the action that his/her considers as appropriate to the actual situation and regarding the prioritization to give for the underlying KPIs, the actions are deployed, and all inputs are updated after the application of these actions in the physical twin.

Figure 25: Logical Architecture of a Digital Twin for the resilience and Sustainability of the Inland waterway transport.

10 Conclusion

This deliverable focus on the specification of the resilience and sustainability framework of the IWT system. For that purpose, we started to present the four living labs and their corresponding use cases by reviewing their needs, objectives, high-level requirements, and main challenges. This helps to have a clear overview of each living lab and to capture the common and specific features in order to design complementary architectural views of the targeted framework in support of the Digital Twin solution. Once these visions have been provided, a formal definition of the resilient and sustainable Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) is provided, and a mapping between the potential mitigation actions with regard to the hazard, vulnerabilities, and risk scenarios.

Finally, the articulation between the different technological stacks of this framework is proposed. It starts by identifying a potential risk. Once this is done; an analysis and risk management are performed. Finally, a mitigation actions are provided.

In the further work, we will challenge the proposed framework throughout living labs and we will check its implementability and deployability with the rest of ReNEW partners.

11 Appendix

11.1 IWT digital twin use cases

The objective of the section, in its V1 version, is to describe the use cases of the IWT digital twin to be designed in Renew project. Particularly, it describes the use cases associated with core services expected from IWT-DT.

A use case represents the behaviour and the capabilities of the IWT-DT in response to a user's request to achieve a given objective. The diagram depicted in Figure 26 gathers a set of use cases from the point of view of a user with resilience and sustainability objectives.

The proposed use cases are to be refined and discussed with the other WPs and LLs. They will serve as a basis for discussion to identify the capabilities of the IWT-TD to be developed in Renew project. On the one hand, some identified use cases are common to all LLs, and others are more specific. Depending on the objectives and desired functionalities, we have identified: use cases for simulation; use cases for monitoring; and use cases for resilience and sustainability. The tables bellow provides details about proposed use cases.

Postconditions	The activities baseline are stored.
Minimum safeguards	The service baseline can be restored in a previous version.
Trigger	Logging as administrator.
Main success scenarios	To be refined later.
Alternative Solution	To be refined later.

Use case: Create account	
Use case ID:	UC_A_03
Main actor:	Administrator [UC_A_01]
Goal / Context of use / Brief description	This use case enables the administrator to create accounts associated with users and unique identifier.
Preconditions	A request is made to create a user account. The user is identified as a stakeholder.
Postconditions	A count is created.
Main success scenarios	To be refined later.
Alternative Solution	To be refined later.

Use case: Manage service access	
Use case ID:	UC_
Main actor:	Administrator
Goal / Context of use / Brief description	Depending on the user's activity, the administrator sets the user's prerogatives.
Preconditions	Account created.
Postconditions	Have access to specified services.
Main success scenarios	To be refined later.
Alternative Solution	To be refined later.

Use case: Launch HIM	
Use case ID:	UC_
Main actor:	User

Goal / Context of use / Brief description	This use case enables to lunch the workspace of IWT DT services.
Preconditions	The user is logged in.
Postconditions	The services associated with the authenticated account are unlocked.
Main success scenarios	To be refined later.
Alternative Solution	To be refined later.

Use case: Set scenario for simulation	
Use case ID:	UC_
Main actor:	User
Goal / Context of use / Brief description	<p>This use case begins when the user launches the simulation workspace. It enables to set up and run a simulation of the IWT framework.</p> <p>Through this use case, the user can:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Configure obstruction scenarios; - Configure climatic parameters; - Configure hydraulic parameters; - Configure infrastructure parameters; - Configure parameters relating to the fleet to be deployed; - Configure missions for deployed vehicles; - Configure position and type of intermodal transport;
Preconditions	The user has logged in and has the required authorization level.
Postconditions	The simulation workplace is launched, the model's libraries are loaded, and the API's are listed.
Main success scenarios	To be refined later.
Alternative Solution	To be refined later.

Use case: Display Planner	
Use case ID:	UC_
Main actor:	User
Goal / Context of use / Brief description	<p>This use case launches a planner to organize deployment and operations. Furthermore, it displays a map of an operational zone. This map displays the status of IWT items such as vessels, infrastructures, water, weather and associated functionalities. It is possible to filter the type of items to be displayed by unchecking them in the setting tab.</p>
Preconditions	The user has logged in and has the required authorization level.
Postconditions	The operating map launched.

Main success scenarios	To be refined later.
Alternative Solution	To be refined later.

Use case: Display Vessel Monitor	
Use case ID:	UC_
Main actor:	User
Goal / Context of use / Brief description	This use case displays vessel on the map in real time, monitor their operational status, and displays their features and performances indicators. The confidential information is only accessible to authorized users.
Preconditions	The user has logged in and has the required authorization level.
Postconditions	Interactive map is displayed.
Main success scenarios	To be refined later.
Alternative Solution	To be refined later.

Use case: Monitor the logistics	
Use case ID:	UC_U_
Main actor:	User
Goal / Context of use / Brief description	This use case is used to manage activities related to logistics operations. It enables to: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Schedule a task; - Analyse the smoothness of navigation; - Calculate performance and competitiveness indicators; - Verify energy availability; - Verify compliance with operating rules and standards. The rules may be environmental, wellbeing or behavioural.
Preconditions	The user has logged in and has the required authorization level.
Postconditions	Logistics information provided.
Main success scenarios	To be refined later.
Alternative paths Solution	To be refined later.

Use case: Plan Task	
Use case ID:	UC_U_
Main actor:	User

Goal / Context of use / Brief description	This use case enables sending planning requests and checking the availability of operating timeslots.
Preconditions	The user has logged in and has the required authorization level.
Postconditions	Request sent.
Main success scenarios	To be refined later.
Alternative Solution	To be refined later.

Use case: Monitor the Infrastructures	
Use case ID:	UC_U_
Main actor:	User
Goal / Context of use / Brief description	This use case provides the operational states and a performance analysis of the infrastructures. Furthermore, it enables to: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Identify the infrastructures; - Monitor the operational status; - Quantify the operational indicators; - Monitor the operational capacity.
Preconditions	The user has logged in and has the required authorization level.
Postconditions	Infrastructures information is displayed.
Main success scenarios	To be refined later.
Alternative Solution	To be refined later.

Use case: Interact with the Map	
Use case ID:	UC_U_
Main actor:	User
Goal / Context of use / Brief description	This use case provides a toolkit to interact with the planner and with the map.
Preconditions	The user has logged in and has the required authorization level.
Postconditions	Responsive interactive mode.
Main success scenarios	To be refined later.
Alternative solution	To be refined later.

Use case: Monitor the hydraulic variation	
Use case ID:	UC_U_
Main actor:	User

Goal / Context of use / Brief description	This use case enables monitoring water variations per navigation section. Minimum and maximum navigation thresholds are identified according to vessel classes. Green is used to indicate navigability, orange to indicate caution, and red to indicate unnavigability. Under given conditions, green may be designated for one class of vessel, but red for a higher class.
Preconditions	The user has logged in and has the required authorization level.
Postconditions	Navigability status displayed.
Main success scenarios	To be refined later.
Alternative solution	To be refined later.

Use case: Assess the States	
Use case ID:	UC_U_
Main actor:	User
Goal / Context of use / Brief description	This use case relies on measurements, calculations and predictions to assess the operating status and performance level of systems. In addition, it enables predictions to be made about future state and behaviour. This use case is characterized by different skills, and calls on several functionalities such as analysis, prediction, optimization, forecasting, evaluation, mitigation of undesirable effects. Through this use case, it is possible to: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Predict water levels; - Analyse risk; - Make meteorological predictions - Decide on deployment and mitigation strategies
Preconditions	The user has logged in and has the required authorization level.
Postconditions	Calculate and provide indicators regarding operational states.
Main success scenarios	To be refined later.
Alternative solution	To be refined later.

Use case: Make Decision	
Use case ID:	UC_U_
Main actor:	User
Goal / Context of use / Brief description	This use case relies on assessments, metrics and KPIs to find emergency deployment plans, reroute the traffic and plan maintenance operations in order to optimize performances and reduces disruptions effect.
Preconditions	The user has logged in and has the required authorization level.
Postconditions	Generate Decision, recommendation or warning.

Main success scenarios	To be refined later.
Alternative solution	To be refined later.

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